

Measuring the dynamics of service accessibility by bus in England: a comparison of scheduled and observed travel time variability

Zihao Chen^{*1,2} and Federico Botta^{†1}

¹Department of Computer Science, University of Exeter

²Department of Mathematics and Statistics, University of Exeter

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Summary

This work presents a national-scale framework for measuring bus-based accessibility using real-time operational data from the UK’s Bus Open Data Service. By matching real-time vehicle locations to scheduled timetables, we construct corrected, routable schedules that reflect how services actually operated. Using these empirical timetables with the R⁵ routing engine, we compute travel times from every LSOA to essential services and derive measures of travel time variability at multiple temporal scales. Case studies reveal widespread gaps between scheduled and observed accessibility and strong urban–rural inequalities. The results highlight the value of operational data for improving accessibility measurement and transport planning.

KEYWORDS: Public Transport Accessibility; Travel Time Variability; GTFS; Inequality; Bus Data

1 Introduction

Fair access to essential services such as healthcare, education and grocery shops is fundamental to spatial justice and transport equity. Poor public transport access to services can lead to social exclusion, reduced wellbeing, and diminished life opportunities (Farber et al., 2011; Lucas, 2012; Stanley et al., 2022), resulting in what are often termed transport deserts (Jiao and Dillivan, 2013). Substantial research has sought to measure accessibility in order to identify and address this geography of inequalities (Hernandez, 2018; Freiberg et al., 2024; Verduzco Torres and McArthur, 2024).

Travel time is often instrumental in accessibility measurement, as it captures the effective cost borne by travellers more directly than physical distance. Common indicators include cumulative opportunity measures (Wachs and Kumagai, 1973) and minimum travel time to the nearest service. In the UK, the Department for Transport publishes journey time statistics (Department for

*zihao.chen@exeter.ac.uk

†f.botta@exeter.ac.uk

Transport, 2019) based on idealised weekday peak hour conditions. However, such metrics typically rely on static timetables or single time windows, overlooking temporal variability and operational uncertainty arising from congestion, weather, and service disruptions. This often leads to overestimation of accessibility (Liu et al., 2023; Lee and Kim, 2023; Chen et al., 2017; Javanmard et al., 2025).

Previous work has attempted to address these problems. Farber et al. (2014) demonstrated the importance of temporal dynamics by calculating minute-by-minute public transport travel times over an entire day to examine its variability, while Wessel et al. (2017) proposed reconstructing routable retrospective timetables from operational data to reveal gaps between scheduled and realised accessibility. More recently, Javanmard et al. (2025) and Braga et al. (2026) addressed the day-to-day travel time variability issue by correcting published timetables using percentile-based observed travel times calculated across different days, highlighting a critical link between transit reliability and accessibility inequalities. Despite these advances, national-scale empirical evidence on travel time variability (TTV) itself remains scarce, largely due to the limited availability of high-frequency operational data. Other forms of TTV, such as within-day variability, which impacts certain types of time-critical trips more, also remain under-explored.

The introduction of the UK Bus Open Data Service (BODS) (Department for Transport, 2020) enables this gap to be addressed. Building on our previous timetable-based analysis (Chen and Botta, 2025), this work uses large-scale real-time bus data for England to construct empirical accessibility measures and to quantify spatial and temporal patterns in travel time variability.

2 Data

We retrieved bus timetable and location data from the Bus Open Data Service (BODS) in GTFS and GTFS-RT formats, as these de-facto international standards facilitate reproducibility and are required by mainstream routing engines such as R⁵ and OpenTripPlanner.

Because BODS provides only live API feeds and does not maintain an archive of historical real-time vehicle locations as of January 2026, we implemented an automated data collection pipeline to continuously download and store national-scale GTFS-RT feeds every 30 seconds. In parallel, complete GTFS timetable snapshots were archived daily. This archiving strategy enables retrospective matching of observed vehicle locations to published timetables and the construction of an empirically corrected timetable.

3 Methodology

Here we briefly describe the method used to construct a corrected empirical timetable. The approach builds on the method proposed by Wessel et al. (2017) and related work, but introduces several adaptations that substantially improve computational efficiency while preserving the accuracy required for large-scale accessibility analysis. We also highlight optimisations developed specifically for UK data which may or may not be applicable to other data.

Real-time data feeds (GTFS-RT) are distributed as Protocol Buffer (PBF) files and were first de-

coded into Python objects before being converted into tabular CSV format following the official specification (General Transit Feed Specification, 2025). Although GTFS-RT feeds may include trip updates, vehicle positions, and service alerts, BODS provides only vehicle position messages, meaning that stop-level delay information must be inferred from vehicle trajectories¹. All records collected within the same day were merged and duplicate observations removed, substantially reducing data volume while retaining full spatio-temporal coverage.

Matching real-time observations to scheduled services requires each vehicle position record to contain a valid *trip_id*, which links it to a corresponding scheduled *trip* within the GTFS bundle. Records lacking this identifier cannot be matched directly; while prior work has attempted to infer missing identifiers using vehicle IDs (Open Innovations, 2024, 2025), we found such approaches yielded only marginal improvements.

For each matchable record, we retrieved the scheduled *route* and ordered sequence of *stops*. Candidate stops were first identified using a coarse spatial filter² that selected stops within approximately 200 m of the vehicle’s reported position, reducing computational cost relative to exhaustive distance calculations. Exact distances were then computed for candidate stops (if found), and the closest stop was retained together with the observation timestamp and distance. Repeating this procedure for all records produced a dense set of vehicle–stop associations over time.

These associations were used to infer stop-level arrival times by retaining, for each stop–trip pair, the observation with the smallest vehicle–stop distance. The corresponding timestamp was substituted for the scheduled arrival time in the GTFS *stop_times.txt* file. Unlike the interpolation-based method of Wessel et al. (2017), this approach does not seek to reconstruct the precise moment at which vehicles dwell at stops, but instead prioritises scalability for national accessibility modelling, where cumulative end-to-end delays matter more than punctuality at individual stops.

The final output is a corrected GTFS feed containing only operated/tracked services and empirically derived stop-level times, which can be used directly in routing engines to compute observed travel times.

Several further optimisations were implemented for BODS. Because some *trip_ids* present in operational data were absent from same-day timetable archives, we expanded matching to include GTFS feeds from up to seven days before and after each observation date, increasing match rates by up to 20% on some days. In addition, when intermediate stops along a route were not directly observed, typically due to vehicles passing quickly or coarse sampling intervals, we interpolated arrival times using neighbouring matched stops, enabling complete trip trajectories to be reconstructed.

¹This also implies that our matching procedure can be easily adapted to other forms of real-time vehicle location data, not only GTFS-RT, provided that the data include a trip-level identifier that allows observations to be linked to a corresponding timetable (see further details below).

²This is implemented by comparing the vehicle’s latitude and longitude to those of each stop and filtering stops within approximately 200 metres in either direction, which substantially reduces computational cost compared with calculating exact distances to all stops along the route.

4 Case Studies

To demonstrate how the corrected timetable reveals gaps between scheduled and observed accessibility, as well as day-to-day variability over extended periods, we present a set of case studies using England-wide BODS data from May to October 2025.

The matching procedure was applied to each day in the study period, producing a corrected timetable that was passed to R⁵py, a Python interface to the R⁵ routing engine for fast multimodal routing (Fink et al., 2022). Bus travel times from each Lower layer Super Output Area (LSOA) to selected essential services were computed for multiple departure times, and summarised using their mean and standard deviation to characterise typical travel time and travel time variability (TTV).

We first analysed within-day travel time and TTV for journeys to hospitals³. Hourly travel times from 7:00 to 17:00 were calculated from each LSOA to all hospitals, retaining the shortest time in each hour. Scheduled travel times and TTV for a representative weekday (the second Tuesday of each month) were used as a benchmark, while observed travel times and TTV from July to October 2025 were averaged across weekdays. Figure 1 maps the resulting gaps between scheduled and observed average travel time and TTV. Across the study period, 79.3% of LSOAs experienced longer observed average travel times than scheduled (79.9% for urban and 76.2% for rural), while 81.6% exhibited higher observed TTV (86.3% for urban and 57.7% for rural). Notably some LSOAs experienced shorter observed average travel times and TTV compared to scheduled ones, which could be due to various reasons such as operators overestimating operational delays when scheduling Wessel et al. (2017). Overall these findings are consistent with existing work which showed a mix of over and under-estimation of travel times using schedule data alone.

³The hospitals used were from the Estates Return Information Collection (ERIC) Site Data for year 2024/25 published by NHS Digital (NHS England Digital, 2024). We used the same selection criteria as the DfT Journey Time Statistics to include only the NHS ‘general’ hospitals. For details: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/journey-time-statistics-guidance/journey-time-statistics-notes-and-definitions-2019>

Figure 1: Maps of the **gaps** between scheduled and observed average travel time and travel time variability (TTV) for journeys from each LSOA in England to the nearest **hospital**. **Red** indicates observed travel time and TTV are higher than scheduled while **blue** indicates the opposite. LSOAs shown in **grey** are unable to reach a hospital by bus within two hours.

We next examined day-to-day travel time variability during the morning peak. Travel times from each LSOA to nearby town centres⁴ were calculated at one-minute intervals between 08:00 and 10:00 on each weekday across the study period, producing 120 travel time estimates per origin-destination pair per day. Minimum, median, and 85th percentile travel times were extracted for each two-hour window. Day-to-day TTV is defined as the standard deviation of these travel times, while average travel time is their mean. Figure 2 reveals a general positive correlation between TTV and average travel time, with urban areas exhibiting lower values for both metrics, while rural areas tend to show higher variability and longer travel times. Overall, the distribution highlights the urban-rural divide in accessibility.

⁴We used locations of English town centres in 2004 from the DLUHC (Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities) Town Centres and retail planning statistics for England and Wales.

Figure 2: **Scatterplot** of travel time variability (TTV) versus average travel time for trips from each LSOA in England to the nearby town centre, with points color-coded by settlement type (urban/rural). Minimum, median, and 85th percentile travel times were calculated for travel times between 8:00 and 10:00 on each weekday from May to October 2025.

5 Conclusion

This paper has presented a framework for constructing empirical measures of bus transport accessibility and its dynamics using national-scale real-time operational data. By matching GTFS-RT vehicle location feeds with scheduled GTFS timetables, we developed a computationally efficient procedure that reconstructs observed stop-level arrival/departure times and produces a corrected, routable timetable reflecting how the bus network actually operated.

Despite these advances, several limitations remain. Reconstructed travel times are retrospective and assume perfect traveller information which may not be realisable in real life, although increasing availability of real-time passenger information suggests this gap is narrowing. In addition, incomplete *trip_id* coverage in BODS prevents some vehicle records from being matched.

Applying this framework to half a year of BODS data for England, we computed travel times from every LSOA to selected essential services and derived measures of multiple forms of travel time variability that reveal pronounced spatial and temporal inequalities and systematic gaps between scheduled and observed accessibility, providing an evidence base for more informed transport planning, service monitoring, and equity-focused policy interventions.

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7 Biography

Zihao Chen is a PhD Candidate at the UKRI Centre for Doctoral Training in Environmental Intelligence. His research involves using large-scale public transport data to measure accessibility to essential services, with a particular focus on bus travel time variability, real-time operational data, and spatial inequalities in access across England.

Federico Botta is a Senior Lecturer in data science in the Department of Computer Science at the University of Exeter. His research aims to provide a deeper understanding of society and human behaviour, both at the collective and individual level, by analysing large novel data streams. He uses tools from data science, network theory, behavioural and computational social sciences to analyse these data sets and investigate different aspects of human behaviour.

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